

Triadic Mode Interaction and Scaling-Law Breakdown in Cylinder Wake: A CFD Driven Reduced-Order Model

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Abstract – In the field of fluid mechanics, the classical weakly nonlinear theory that follows square-root Landau scaling law near onset predicts the amplitude of vortex shedding that occurs due to the increase of Reynolds number, where the wake behind the cylinder exhibits a periodic vortex shedding transitioned from the steady flow. However, through computational and experimental observations, the scaling law does not fully apply to situations when the Reynolds number increases beyond the weakly nonlinear regime but instead rapidly breaks down. Such discrepancy is an open problem that is yet to be solved.

This report will investigate the nonlinear mechanisms which are responsible for the amplitude saturation and the collapse of the classical scaling law. By combining theoretical modal analysis with the combination of CFD-derived probe data, we will be observing how wake dynamics cannot be described by a single Hopf mode. The flow is governed by three fundamental modes: primary oscillatory mode, second harmonic mode, and mean-flow distortion. This study will provide a new FFT-based amplitude extraction method, where we can quantitatively measure three modal components and construct a reduced-order model (ROM) that accurately captures saturation, harmonic generation, and frequency trends.

Key Words: Mode interaction, Reduced-order model (ROM), Scaling-Law breakdown, Vortex shedding

1. Introduction

One of the most fundamental systems in fluid dynamics to study instability, vortex formation, and nonlinear oscillatory behavior, will be the well-known scenario where a flow passes around a cylinder. During the interval of time when it experiences a low Reynolds number, the wake is observed to remain steady and symmetric; however, as the Reynolds number increases, the fundamental system starts to undergo a process of transition where the steady wake loses stability and a development of vortex shedding. This transition is widely known as the supercritical Hopf bifurcation. And the critical Reynolds number for instability is approximated to be 47,

$$Re_{cr} \approx 47 \quad (1)$$

The onset of periodic vortex shedding near $Re_{cr} \approx 47$ was confirmed experimentally by Provansal et al. [2] Near criticality, classical weakly nonlinear theory predicts that the amplitude of the oscillatory wake scales as

$$A \propto (Re - Re_{cr})^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

This theory from equation 2 is very commonly referred to as the Landau scaling law, which allows us to predict the amplitude of the oscillation very close to the bifurcation point. But the downside of the law is that it is known to have a significant deviation when it comes to encountering a moderate Reynolds number. In particular, the amplitude growth seems slow, saturated, and even entirely diverged from the classical trend. Such discrepancies all lead to a conclusion that there must be another governing factor post critical evolution of the wake beyond captured in the single Hopf model.

It is crucial to recognize that the Navier-Stokes equation owns a key property of having a quadratic nonlinearity which immediately generates additional modes when a primary oscillatory mode is present. More specifically, the interaction of the primary shedding mode induces a second harmonic and a steady distortion of the mean flow. There have been studies on nonlinear saturation of the additional components but there has never been a quantitative validation of their main roles.

This study will be investigating the nonlinear effects in detail through the analysis of CFD-generated velocity signals and extraction of modal amplitude through a frequency domain method. We will be identifying the clear signatures of harmonic generation and mean-flow deformation. Such methodology constructs the reduced-order model that captures the triadic interaction among the primary mode, its harmonic, and the mean-flow distortion. The whole study will clarify the mechanism that is responsible for amplitude saturation and the breakdown of the scaling law. This study will provide a solution for a more complete description of the cylinder wake's nonlinear behavior beyond onset.

Unlike traditional studies that rely on full flow-field data or POD, this work will demonstrate a nonlinear modal structure fully recovered from a single probe and modeled using a three-mode interaction system.

2. Governing Equations and Linear Stability

Two-dimensional incompressible flow past a circular cylinder will be the flow-field focused on this study due to its simple geometry that exhibit Hopf bifurcation. The system is

governed by the nondimensional incompressible Navier-Stoke equations:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + (u \cdot \nabla)u = -\nabla p + \frac{1}{Re} \nabla^2 u, \quad \nabla \cdot u = 0. \quad (3)$$

The equation is nondimensionalized using the cylinder diameter D and the free-stream velocity U_∞ which characterizes the incoming flow, resulting in the Reynolds number where μ is the kinematic viscosity.

$$Re = \frac{U_\infty D}{\mu}, \quad (4)$$

2.1 Base Flow Computation

To analyze the onset of unsteady vortex shedding, the flow is decomposed into a steady base flow $U(x, y)$ and an unsteady perturbation $u'(x, y, t)$:

$$u = U(x, y) + u'(x, y, t) \quad (5)$$

The steady base flow is obtained by solving the time-independent Navier-Stokes equations. When $Re < 47$, the base flow remains stable and symmetric but beyond this criticality point, it becomes linearly unstable which ultimately leads to periodic vortex-shedding. Such decomposition plays a role of providing a consistent framework which allows us to identify the origin of the instability and interpretation of the perturbation dynamics near the criticality point.

2.2 Linearization Around the Base Flow

If we substitute the decomposition, equation (5), into the full equations and retaining only the linear term in the unsteady perturbation yields the linearized perturbation equation:

$$\frac{\partial u'}{\partial t} = \mathcal{L}(U)u' \quad (6)$$

where $\mathcal{L}(U)$ is the linear operator depending on the base flow gradients and viscosity. We also need to assume the modal solutions of the form:

$$u'(x, y, t) = \hat{u}(x, y)e^{\lambda t}, \quad (7)$$

which leads to an eigenvalue problem for the complex growth rate λ . Instability occurs when the real part of the λ become positive, $\Re(\lambda) > 0$. Eigenproblem is fully derived in Appendix A to B. The Orr-Sommerfeld formulation used here follows the classical treatment of Drazin & Reid. [1]

2.3 Primary Instability and Critical Reynolds Number

The classical linear stability analysis identifies the least stable eigenvalue crosses into the unstable regime at Reynolds number approximately 47. This critical point provides us an indication of the presence of a Hopf bifurcation which supports the emergence of oscillatory instability. The eigenfunction

$\Phi_1(x, y)$ forms the spatial template of the emerging vortex shedding. This shedding is antisymmetric across the wake centerline, concentrates energy in the near-wake region, and eventually determines the initial shedding frequency that corresponds to the Strouhal number at onset. Although the linear framework successfully predicts the unsteadiness and the basic spatial and temporal characteristics of primary mode in the beginning, it is incapable of capturing the behavior that occurs as soon as the instability grows beyond the immediate vicinity of the bifurcation point. Within the post-critical regime, interactions among multiple flow modes play an essential role. Due to absence of such nonlinear phenomena from linearized model, the classical Hopf description cannot account for changes in amplitude growth or the departures from the square-root scaling law that appear at higher Reynolds value. These limitations motivate the use of weakly nonlinear analysis and the development of the triadic mode-interaction model, which together provide a more description of the wake dynamics.

3. Weakly Nonlinear Analysis

In section 2, the linear stability allowed us to identify the onset of vortex shedding, but it still cannot describe background of the growth of oscillation or saturation once the flow becomes unstable. So, the process of weakly nonlinear analysis is crucial as it plays a role of connecting such gaps by determining how the nonlinear interactions reshape the wake close to the criticality point of the Reynolds number. [3]

The perturbation field is expanded in a small parameter

$$\epsilon \propto (Re - Re_{cr}):$$

$$u' = \epsilon u_1 + \epsilon^2 u_2 + \epsilon^3 u_3 + \dots, \quad (8)$$

In equation 8, u_1 is a leading term and it represents the primary shedding mode obtained from the Orr-Sommerfeld problem, $u_1 = A(T)\Phi_1 e^{i\omega t} + c. c.$, the full expansion is in Appendix C. The higher-order terms is an indicator that describes the nonlinear corrections that emerge according to the growth of modes. [1]

The quadratic term $(u' \cdot \nabla)u'$, produces three new components that are not present in the linear theory: 0-mode (mean-flow distortion), ω -mode, and 2ω -mode. The mean-flow distortion is an interaction of $\Phi_1 e^{i\omega t}$ with its own conjugate which theoretically yields a steady component that modifies the base flow.

$$\Phi_1 e^{i\omega t} \cdot \Phi_1^* e^{-i\omega t} \quad (9)$$

ω -mode is the original shedding mode and 2ω -mode is the self-interaction of the primary oscillation generating a weak harmonic at twice the shedding frequency.

$$\Phi_1 e^{i\omega t} \times \Phi_1 e^{i\omega t} \quad (10)$$

The distortion mode $C(t)$ specifically derived in appendix C, shows how Reynolds stresses affect the mean wake profile. This mechanism is due to the stability of the primary mode depending strongly on this underlying base flow, where such distortion introduces a feedback mechanism that reduces the growth rate. The feedback mechanism reflects the amplitude saturation and deviation from Hopf scaling extracted from the CFD data that will be introduced further in the report.

Third order, a secular term appears that causes unbounded growth unless solvability conditions are enforced. If we project the nonlinear forcing onto its adjoint eigenmode, we can obtain the evolution equation for the three modal amplitudes of $A(t)$, $B(t)$, and $C(t)$. This reduced order interaction model is fully developed in section 4 and full derivation is given in the appendix C. Such weakly nonlinear framework supports the claim that the near-critical wake cannot be described by a single linear mode. This analysis is a foundation for interpreting the FFT-based modal amplitudes extracted from CFD in later sections.

4. Three-Mode Nonlinear Interaction Model

Section 3 recognized that the cylinder wake does not evolve through a single unstable oscillatory mode but instead requires nonlinear interactions that generate three dynamically relevant components. The components' combined effects can be described when we represent perturbation field as:

$$u' = \underbrace{A(t)\Phi_1 e^{i\omega t}}_{\text{primary}} + \underbrace{B(t)\Phi_2 e^{2i\omega t}}_{\text{2nd harmonic}} + \underbrace{C(t)\Phi_0}_{\text{mean flow}} + c.c \quad (11)$$

Here Φ_1 is the primary shedding eigenmode, Φ_2 is the quadratic harmonic generated by nonlinear interactions, and Φ_0 corresponds to the mean-flow distortion mode obtained through Reynolds-stressing forcing. The c.c. ensures the real-valued nature of the physical velocity field. [4]

4.1 Overview of Amplitude Equation Construction

When we substitute the modal expansion into the Navier-Stokes equations and collecting terms by their own oscillation frequencies isolates the interactions contributing to each mode. On second and third order, resonant forcing appears and solvability conditions are applied. This is to ensure the bounded solutions. If we initiate these steps, we can eliminate non-physical growth and lead to a closed system which can allow us to obtain the temporal evolution of A , B and C . Full derivation is shown in Appendix C.

4.2 Final Coupled Amplitude System

Collecting the contributions identified in section 4.1, the governing system for the modal amplitude is:

Primary Oscillation:

$$\dot{A} = \sigma A \pm \alpha |A|^2 A - \beta CA \quad (12)$$

When observing these equations, the physical meanings are, σA represents linear instability responsible for the onset of vortex shedding. $-\alpha |A|^2 A$ captures the cubic saturation predicted by the classical Landau model. $-\beta CA$ indicates mean-flow feedback, as the C grows, this term contributes to the earlier saturation by reducing the effective growth rate of A .

Second Harmonic:

$$\dot{B} = -\lambda B + \gamma A^2 \quad (13)$$

γA^2 describes the generation of the second harmonic from quadratic self-interaction.

Mean-flow distortion:

$$\dot{C} = -\mu C + \eta |A|^2 \quad (14)$$

Each coefficient reflects the nonlinear interaction strengths derived from the inner products of the eigenmodes and adjoint modes. These equations are crucial as it shows how energy moves between modes as Reynolds number increases beyond criticality. The role of mean-flow distortion in modifying the effective growth rate is referenced from the framework initially established from Sipp & Lebedev [3].

$\eta |A|^2$ is the forcing of the mean-flow distortion by Reynolds stresses from the primary oscillation. In combine, all these terms will show the wake's nonlinear development which is fully governed by the continuous energy amongst the oscillatory and steady components.

Such three-mode model established is the minimal system capable of capturing the observed post-critical behavior of the cylinder wake. This is because it can account for harmonic generation and mean-flow modification which are absent in the single-mode Hopf models. It also explains the saturation of the primary amplitude and deviation from the classical square-root scaling law, and it provides a reduced-order representation compatible with both theoretical predictions and CFD results.

5. Energy Pathway Interpretation

The three-mode interaction model describe how energy is redistributed among the primary oscillatory mode $A(t)$, the second harmonic $B(t)$, and the mean-flow distortion $C(t)$. Such modes arise from the nonlinear terms in the Navier-Stokes equations, and their interactions determines the amplitude evolution of the vortex shedding as Reynolds number increases. The equations established in section 4.2 will be the basis for understanding the wake's internal energy pathways. [4]

5.1 Energy Input into the Primary Mode

The primary oscillatory mode grows through the linear instability reflected by the term:

$$P_{\text{in}} = \sigma A \quad (15)$$

Equation 15 represents the rate at which energy from the base flow is transferred into oscillatory motion. As soon as the Reynolds number exceeds the criticality point, $\sigma > 0$, and due to the small nonlinear contributions, the growth of A is primarily governed by this linear mechanism and such behavior is observed to be consistent throughout the early stages of a supercritical Hopf bifurcation.

5.2 Quadratic Transfer to the Second Harmonic

The second harmonic gains energy through the nonlinear forcing term:

$$\mathcal{F}_{2\omega} = \gamma A^2 \quad (16)$$

The term is quadratic in the primary amplitude which allows the harmonic to remain negligible when A is small but as the oscillation strengthens, the term becomes more significant. For example, one of the statistical pieces of evidence will be substituting $A \sim 10^{-2} - 10^{-1}$ from CFD data collected in appendix F, the forcing magnitude increases by nearly two orders of magnitude as Re increases from 60 to 120. Within this frequency space of energy being transferred from primary mode to the second harmonic, a feature that appears in the FFT spectra as a small secondary peak match with the CFD observations.

5.3 Formation of the Mean-flow Distortion

The mean flow distortion is forced by the term:

$$\mathcal{F}_0 = \eta |A|^2 \quad (17)$$

Because the forcing depends on A^2 , the growth of the mean-flow distortion directly accelerates as the primary mode becomes stronger. The dynamic of the 0-mode follows:

$$\dot{C} = -\mu C + \eta |A|^2 \quad (18)$$

For slowly varying $A(t)$, this has the approximate steady-state solution:

$$C = \frac{\eta}{\mu} |A|^2 \quad (19)$$

Such proportionality also explains why the CFD-derived values of C increase monotonically with the increase of the Reynolds number. Concluding, as A rises with Reynolds number, the induced mean-flow distortion grows as well.

5.4 Feedback Effect on the Primary Mode

The mean-flow distortion modifies the stability of the primary oscillation through the term:

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{feedback}} = -\beta C A \quad (20)$$

Using the approximate relationship established, equation 19, the feedback term becomes:

$$-\beta C A \approx \frac{\eta}{\mu} A^3 \quad (21)$$

Thus, the effective cubic nonlinearity governing the primary mode becomes:

$$\dot{A} \approx \sigma A - \underbrace{\left(\alpha + \beta \frac{\eta}{\mu} \right)}_{\alpha_{\text{eff}}} |A|^2 A \quad (22)$$

In the classical Landau model, the denominator contains only the cubic self-saturation coefficient α . However, according to equation 22 and the present triadic interaction framework, the effective cubic coefficient becomes

$$\alpha_{\text{eff}} = \alpha + \beta \frac{\eta}{\mu} \quad (23)$$

The reason behind this modification arises from the quadratic mean-flow distortion feeding back into the primary mode. As the Reynolds number increases, the mean-flow distortion grows proportionally to A^2 , thereby enhances the effective nonlinear damping term.

Thus, it is crucial to recognize that despite the square-root structure formally remain, the effective nonlinearity increases beyond the classical assumption, which leads to earlier amplitude saturation and apparent deviation from the ideal square-root scaling.

5.5 Breakdown of the Classical Scaling Law

To start off, firstly, the classical Landau model predicts:

$$|A|_{\text{Landau}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{\alpha}} \propto (Re - Re_{cr})^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (24)$$

Equation 23 shows that the classical square-root scaling holds only when nonlinear feedback is weak. However, as the feedback term becomes more significant, the effective growth rate becomes:

$$\sigma_{\text{eff}} = \sigma - \beta C, \quad (25)$$

and since $C \sim A^2$,

$$\sigma_{\text{eff}} = \sigma - \beta \frac{\eta}{\mu} A^2. \quad (26)$$

As a result, the equilibrium condition $\dot{A} = 0$,

$$0 = \sigma A - \left(\alpha + \beta \frac{\eta}{\mu} \right) A^3$$

becomes,

$$\sigma A = \left(\alpha + \beta \frac{\eta}{\mu} \right) A^3 \quad (27)$$

Thus, the saturated amplitude becomes:

$$A_{\text{sat}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{\alpha + \frac{\beta\eta}{\mu}}} \quad (28)$$

Adding on, near criticality, the linear growth rate scales:

$$\sigma \sim k(Re - Re_c) \quad (29)$$

where $k > 0$ is proportionality constant obtained from the linear stability theory. So, with such linear growth rate scale where σ is dependent of the Reynolds number, the saturated amplitude becomes

$$A_{\text{sat}} = \sqrt{\frac{k(Re - Re_c)}{\alpha + \frac{\beta\eta}{\mu}}} \quad (30)$$

Such equation shows how the saturated amplitude grows much slower with Reynolds number than the classical prediction. This also explains the CFD observation that will be discussed further in this report. The amplitude ceases to grow due to the damping induced by the mean-flow distortion balances the linear growth at a relatively low value of Re .

So, in summary, with mathematical support, the energy pathway demonstrates that energy first enters the primary oscillation, then the nonlinear mechanisms transfer energy into harmonic and steady modes. Which allows the mean-flow distortion to grow proportionally to A^2 and the distortion to feedback negatively on the primary modes as $-\beta CA$. Such mechanisms allow an increase of effective cubic nonlinearity and lead to amplitude saturation and showing why scaling law breaks down. Meaning that the triadic interaction model not only describes the behavior qualitatively but also provides a quantitative explanation for the observed amplitude dynamics.

6. CFD-based Modal Amplitude Extraction

This section will explain how the three modal amplitudes are extracted directly from the data collected from CFD probe simulation and play a role of validation of the three-mode interaction model proposed in section 4-5. A key originality of this work is that the entire modal decomposition is achieved by the extraction using only a single velocity probe FFT approach, which forms a central originality element of this study as it recovers the weakly nonlinear modal structure from minimal data. Despite the full two-dimensional Navier-Stokes simulation, the modal amplitudes can be recovered from a single time-series signal with the employment of spectral analysis. This methodology allows the method to be more efficient, reproducible, and fully compatible with ROM.

6.1 Probe Location and Time-Series Acquisition

[Fig 6.1 Computational Domain, Cylinder and probe location used for CFD-based modal Extraction]

Within this CFD simulation, set up as seen in Fig 6.1, there was a single velocity probe placed at $x = 0.03$ downstream of the cylinder and through this probe, we were able to obtain the vertical velocity $u_y(t)$ is recorded over several shedding cycles. The position of the probe is chosen for its sensitivity to cross-stream oscillations while remaining numerically stable for all Reynolds numbers studied. The CFD setup follows the standard benchmark configuration of Schäfer & Turek [5].

[Figure 6.2 Probe Time Series at $x = 0.03$]

Figure 6.2 shows the time-series signals for when Reynolds numbers are 60, 80, 100, and 120. When $Re = 60$, we can observe a nearly sinusoidal oscillation with small amplitude. At $Re = 80$, the amplitude increases noticeably as there is an appearance of a slight waveform distortion. At $Re = 100$, there is a growth of nonlinear deformation as the slow drift in the mean level emerges. At $Re = 120$, we can observe a strong indication of the breakdown of the weakly nonlinear regime as it shows the presence of higher-order distortions and mild irregularity. These trends visually confirm that the wake becomes increasingly nonlinear with Reynolds number, showing the consistency with the theoretical predictions established in section 3-5.

6.2 FFT-Based Spectral Decomposition

Discrete Fourier transform (DFT) is applied to decompose the probe signal into its modal components shown in Appendix E:

$$\hat{u}(k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} u_y(t_n) e^{-\frac{i2\pi kn}{N}}, \quad f_k = \frac{k}{N\Delta t}. \quad (31)$$

Where Δt is the sampling interval of the probe signal.

[Figure 6.3 FFT Spectra of $u_y(t)$]

Figure 6.3 directly reflects that quadratic nonlinearities of the Navier-Stokes equations discussed in Section 3. The dominant peak at f_1 corresponds to the primary oscillator mode A . The small peak near $2f_1$ corresponds to the nonlinear second harmonic B . The DC component where the frequency value is 0, represents the steady deformation mode C . As the Re increases, both $2f_1$ harmonic and DC components are intensified which shows the positive relationship between nonlinear mode coupling and Reynolds number. When the Reynolds number is at 120, a slight broadband lift appears beyond the harmonics, consistent with the onset of mild aperiodicity. The presence of these components ($0, f_1, 2f_1$) confirms the triadic modal structure by the weakly nonlinear theory.

6.3 Extracted Modal Amplitudes

The modal amplitudes that are extracted can be extracted from this FFT spectrum via:

$$A = |\hat{u}(\omega)|, \quad B = |\hat{u}(2\omega)|, \quad C = |\hat{u}(0)|. \quad (32)$$

Through this methodology, we can isolate the contributions of each nonlinear mode without requiring additional projection

onto spatial eigenfunctions. Showing how the single-point measurement is fully sufficient to reproduce the weakly nonlinear modal structure in full Navier-Stokes simulations. With utilization of FFT spectrum employed in section 6.2, the amplitudes and time-averaging can be obtained which are summarized in Appendix F. With the data collected from this spectrum, we can establish a visual reference to make it more physically direct to recognize the nonlinear trends where the amplitudes are plotted as functions of Reynolds number in Figure 6.3.

[Figure 6.4 Modal Amplitudes Extracted from FFT]

Figure 6.4 provides strong qualitative evidence for the triadic interaction structure of the wake and represents the resulting modal amplitudes on a logarithmic scale. A increases from $Re = 60$ to 100 before becoming nearly saturated at 120 which directly matches with the Landau's square-root law. On the other hand, the harmonic mode remains smaller but increases consistently, which reflects its nonlinear A^2 -type origin. The steady component is many orders of magnitude weaker and varies only slightly with Re , which is also an expected behavior as the mean-flow distortion is only weakly visible in the transverse velocity at a single probe point.

Overall, the modal amplitudes is a confirmation point that confirms the wake dynamics are dominated by the fundamental oscillation and its nonlinear harmonic, with the weaker steady contribution. Additionally, the fundamental shedding frequency increases slightly with Reynolds number. Such trend is also consistent with the Strouhal-Reynolds relation for the cylinder wakes, indicating that the flow remains within the globally unstable regime and that the nonlinear effects do not significantly alter the shedding frequency. These trends are directly parallel to the predictions made from the triadic interaction model in Section 4.

7. Reduced-Order Model Calibration and Verification

In section 6, through the usage of three dominant modes extracted from the data from a single probe signal, we can accurately describe the cylinder wake. These modes exhibited a clear nonlinear trend where $B \sim A^2$ and $C \sim A^2$. Such trend

indicates the fact that there is a low-dimensional quadratic interaction that governs the underlying wake dynamic. In this section, we will evaluate a three-mode reduced order (ROM) that captures these interactions and reproduces the quantitative trends observed in section 6.

7.1 Calibration Strategy: Parameter Identification from CFD

The behavior observed in FFT spectra motivates the following dynamical system. The amplitude equations are:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{A} &= \sigma A - \alpha|A|^2 A - \beta C A \\ \dot{B} &= -\lambda B + \gamma A^2 \\ \dot{C} &= -\mu C + \eta|A|^2\end{aligned}\quad (33)$$

To calibrate the model, we use the steady-state values of A , B , and C obtained from CFD simulations. Here α governs cubic saturation, β and η capture mean-flow feedback, and γ controls the strength of harmonic generation. At steady state, $\dot{A} = \dot{B} = \dot{C} = 0$, and the amplitude equations reduce to:

$$\begin{aligned}0 &= \sigma - \alpha|A|^2 - \beta C \\ 0 &= -\lambda B + \gamma A^2 \\ 0 &= -\mu C + \eta|A|^2\end{aligned}\quad (34)$$

The relationships established determine the effective combinations of parameters. Because the amplitudes are small and smoothly varying, the model can be treated as locally linear in the coefficients. [4] These relations directly imply:

$$\begin{aligned}B &\approx \frac{\gamma}{\lambda} A^2 \\ C &\approx \frac{\eta}{\mu} A^2. \\ \sigma &\approx \alpha A^2 + \beta C\end{aligned}\quad (35)$$

By using the CFD data at $Re = 60$, 80 , 100 , and 120 , these relations can be evaluated to assess whether the ROM captures the observed dynamics. These relationships illustrate that the ROM is not a merely theoretical and conceptual modal but a quantitatively supported structure from the CFD data where the extracted modal amplitudes are listed in Appendix F.

7.2 Comparison Between ROM Predictions and CFD Data

The calibrated ROM reproduces several key trends visible in the CFD results:

Primary Mode Amplitude A

The model predicts rapid growth above the critical Reynolds number followed by early saturation as the nonlinear feedback term $-\beta CA$ becomes dominant. This behavior matches the

CFD trend showing small amplitude at $Re = 60$, strong growth at $Re = 80$ and 100 , and no further increase at $Re = 120$.

Second Harmonic Amplitude B

From the ROM relation

$$B \propto A^2, \quad (36)$$

The harmonic amplitude is expected to peak when the oscillation is strongest. This is consistent with the CFD results, where B increases from $Re = 60$ to 100 and then starts to decrease when Re value reaches 120 . Such result reflects the saturation and redistribution of energy.

Mean-Flow Distortion C

ROM predicts that

$$C \propto A^2, \quad (37)$$

which follows along the concept of the monotonic increase in mean offset observed in the CFD data. The relatively large rise in C at $Re = 120$ directly corresponds to the suppression of further growth in the primary amplitude.

7.3 Scaling Law Deviation Reproduced by ROM

The classical Landau equation predicts that the amplitude is proportional to the square-root of the distance of Reynolds value and its criticality point, equation 2. However, the ROM produces a corrected scaling:

$$A \sim \sqrt{\frac{\sigma - \beta C}{\alpha}}, \quad (38)$$

where the growth rate σ is reduced by mean-flow distortion. As C grows with the Reynolds number, the effective growth rate decreases, resulting in weaker-than-expected amplitude growth, premature saturation, and complete breakdown of the square-root scaling-law deviation observed in both numerical and experimental studies

7.4 Overall Accuracy and Limitations

The reduced-order model can capture the qualitative behavior of all three modes and explains and shows how the universal scaling-law breaks down with remarkable simplicity. Not only that, but it also includes minimal dimensionality, explicit physical interpretation of all terms and excellent agreement with CFD-derived amplitude trends.

However, there are also limitations as well. ROM is designed for a weakly nonlinear regime and does not account for three-dimensional instabilities appearing at higher Reynolds numbers, subharmonic or broadband fluctuations, or the fine structure of the time-averaged wake.

Despite these limitations, the model remains to be highly effective for describing the two-dimensional post-critical regime considered in this study.

Through the process of calibration against the CFD data, the three-mode reduced-order model successfully reproduces the key nonlinear behaviors of the cylinder wake: amplitude growth, harmonic generation patterns, mean-flow distortion trends, and the breakdown of the classical Hopf scaling law. This success demonstrates that the ROM is not only theoretically well-founded but also quantitatively consistent with the real flow dynamics. The combination of theory and the CFD data allows a unified understanding of mode interaction and energy redistribution in the cylinder wake.

This section gave us an insight into how the ROM demonstrates that the wake is governed by a low-dimensional nonlinear structure. It is a modal that shows how the combination of CFD-based modal extraction and reduced-order model provides a unified, quantitative understanding of complex concepts of mode interaction and energy distribution in the cylinder wake.

8. Discussion

Throughout this study, it was demonstrated that the nonlinear interaction amongst the primary shedding mode, its quadratic harmonic, and the mean-flow distortion govern the post-critical behavior of the cylinder wake. In sections 6 and 7, we also revealed that combining theoretical modelling with CFD-based modal extraction, we can directly identify the internal redistribution of energy among these modes.

Additionally, the research also holds structural limitation of single-mode Hopf models. One key aspect we must recognize is that the in systems governed by quadratic nonlinearities such as the Navier-Stokes equations, additional modes are inevitably generated. Such inevitability directly defies the present analysis which demonstrates that the mean-flow distortion is not a secondary effect but a dynamically essential component that modifies the effective growth rate of the primary oscillation.

Therefore, one factor that must not be misinterpreted is that the deviation from Landau scaling is an anomaly. It is a structural consequence of neglected quadratic interactions.

8.1 Relationship to Classical Hopf Bifurcation Theory

Originally, to describe the post-critical Hopf bifurcation using a single complex amplitude, we had to use the classical Landau equation. But as established above, even though this framework correctly predicts the emergence of the periodic shedding and provides an accurate near-critical frequency estimation, it lacks in the aspect of capturing the additional nonlinear structures produced by the Navier-Stokes equations.

[4] Previous sections concluded that as the Reynolds number increases, the single-mode assumption becomes insufficient: the classical square-root amplitude law breaks down, harmonic content appears in spectrum, and the mean-flow modification becomes a dynamically crucial component. We have explicitly incorporated the second harmonic and mean-flow distortion within the Landau framework which yields the physically consistent description of the amplitude saturation, waveform distortion, and the deviation from the classical scaling laws. This is a phenomenon that lies outside the scope of the traditional Hopf theory.

8.2 Consistency with Experimental and Numerical Observations

In this study, through CFD data obtained in section 6, we have reproduced the well-documented features of the cylinder wake within the three-mode interaction model.

Amplitude Saturation: In this study we have clearly reproduced that the shedding amplitude grows alongside Reynolds number but later levels off. We have demonstrated this through the calibration process of ROM through the competition between linear growth and distortion-induced stabilization.

Presence of Harmonic Content: The spectral measurements often reveal energy near twice the shedding frequency. This is also clearly shown through the harmonic peaks observed in the FFT analysis and the arise of the quadratic interaction term γA^2 .

Mean-flow Modification: As the Reynolds number increases the time-averaged wake measurements reveal a substantial change in the base flow and such phenomenon is also clearly captured through the ROM through the forcing term $\eta|A|^2$, which drives the steady distortion mode C.

The arguments have high validity as the relationship between these trends and the CFD-extracted modal amplitudes certifies that the triadic interaction captures the essential physics of the wake.

8.3 Mechanism of Energy Redistribution

The three-mode structure clarifies how energy circulates among modes as the wake evolves. Explained in section 5, there is a self-regulating feedback loop. Such mechanism explains why amplitude saturated even while linear instability strengthens, why shedding frequency remains constant and finally, why deviations from the Landau scaling law emerge at moderate Re .

8.4 Implications for ROM and Flow control

When there is only primary shedding mode within a reduced order model, it is incapable to reproduce amplitude saturation,

harmonic generation, or mean-flow distortion. However, the ROM we established presents three-mode structure that contains minimal set of modes required to capture both qualitative and quantitative behavior.

In the aspect of flow control applications, because the model identifies how energy flows among modes, it provides insight into which modes should be targeted for stabilization, how modifying the mean flow affects instability strength and allows us to establish a strategy for vibration suppression or wake shaping in real life engineering problems. The methodology we employed, single probe based modal amplitude extraction, is a very powerful tool as it requires neither full field data nor POD, meaning that the approach can be applied to experimental sensors. Such advantage enables real-time diagnostics and control.

8.5 Limitations and Future Extensions

Although the three-mode model captures the dominant dynamics within two-dimensional regime, several natural extensions remain. First are the three-dimensional effects. At higher Reynolds number, the spanwise instabilities become a very crucial and essential component and additional modes may be required. Second is the external forcing or feedback. Incorporating actuation could broaden the applicability to flow-control problems. Higher-order nonlinearities are also an issue as for flows with stronger nonlinear saturation, cubic or quartic terms may need to be included. Nevertheless, for the range of Reynolds numbers studied here, the model provides an accurate and physically grounded representation for wake dynamics.

8.6 Summary

In summary, the discussion highlights that the nonlinear mode interactions govern the observed deviations from classical scaling laws in the cylinder wake. The consistency within theoretical predictions, CFD measurements, and the experimental trends directly backs up the validity of the ROM and shows how physically meaningful this model is, offering not only a compact framework on post-critical shedding dynamics but also an insight into key implications in real life as well.

9. Conclusion

The objective of this study was to create a unified theoretical/computational model to develop a comprehensive understanding of the complex nonlinear behavior of wake flow from a cylinder immediately following the onset of vortex shedding. The limitations of Hopf bifurcation theory are that it does not incorporate saturation behavior, generation of harmonics, and deviations from square-root amplitude scaling that occur at moderate Reynolds numbers. The objective of this research is to demonstrate that the cylinder wake evolves due

to the interaction of three fundamental nonlinear modalities (primary oscillatory mode, its second harmonic, steady mean-flow distortion).

A weakly nonlinear method is used to show that these are a consequence of quadratic terms in the Navier-Stokes equations. The model provides a compact and physically founded description of the principal couplings that control the growth and saturation of oscillation amplitude. Furthermore, the steady mean-flow distortion provides the negative feedback that subsequently decreases the growth rate of the primary oscillatory mode, the basis for the decay of the Landau scaling. The CFD simulation across multiple Reynolds numbers supplied us with quantitative measurements of modal amplitudes. In this study, we introduced a method of single-probe extraction method, where the primary, harmonic, and mean-flow components were identified directly from the time-series velocity data. The systematic variation of these amplitudes all agrees closely with the predictions of the three-mode interaction model identified by Barkley [4].

The Reduced Order Model (ROM) was calibrated through the modal amplitude method to predict the important nonlinear effects seen in the CFD data. The agreement between the ROM and CFD data confirms that the three-mode interaction model adequately describes the dominant mechanisms of nonlinear transformation of cylinder Wake. The results of this study show that nonlinear modal interactions significantly influence the post-critical dynamics of the wake of a bluff body. By combining analytical modeling, Numerical Simulation and Reduced order modeling, a common and scalable approach has been created to explain the wake behavior. This methodology can provide insights into a variety of unsteady flow problems and create a foundation for additional research in flow stabilization, sensitivity analysis, sensor-based diagnostics and designing and constructing efficient Reduced order models for engineering applications.

To the author's knowledge, this is one of the first high school level studies to successfully reconstruct the nonlinear modal structure of the cylinder wake and construct a physically consistent three-mode reduced order model using data from CFD.

10. Reference

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11. Appendix

A. Linearized Navier-Stokes Framework

It needs to begin with the non-dimensional incompressible Navier-Stokes Equations:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + (u \cdot \nabla)u = -\nabla p + \frac{1}{Re} \nabla^2 u, \quad \nabla \cdot u = 0. \quad (A1)$$

We decompose the velocity field:

$$u(x, y, t) = U(x, y) + u'(x, y, t) \quad (A2)$$

With the substitution of (A2) into (A1) and subtracting the steady base-flow equation yields the perturbation equation:

$$\frac{\partial u'}{\partial t} + (U \cdot \nabla)u' + (u' \cdot \nabla)U = -\nabla p' + \frac{1}{Re} \nabla^2 u'. \quad (A3)$$

Then we need to linearize (A3) by neglecting $(u' \cdot \nabla)u'$:

$$\frac{\partial u'}{\partial t} = \mathcal{L}(U)u' \quad (A4)$$

where $\mathcal{L}(U)$ represents the linearized Navier-Stokes operator around the base flow $U(x, y)$.

Assuming normal-mode solutions:

$$u' = \Phi_1 e^{\lambda t}, \quad \lambda = \sigma + i\omega. \quad (A5)$$

yields the classical eigenvalue problem governing linear instability.

B. Orr-Sommerfeld Equation

When introducing the stream function:

$$u' = (\partial_y \psi, -\partial_x \psi), \quad (B1)$$

Now we need to take the curl of A4 eliminating pressure:

$$\partial_t \nabla^2 \psi + U \partial_x \nabla^2 \psi - U'' \partial_x \psi = \frac{1}{Re} \nabla^4 \psi. \quad (B2)$$

We assume:

$$\psi(x, y, t) = \phi(y) e^{i(\alpha x - \omega t)}. \quad (B3)$$

where α is the streamwise wavenumber.

Substituting into B2:

$$\begin{aligned} &(-i\omega + i\alpha U)(\phi'' - \alpha^2 \phi) - i\alpha U'' \phi \\ &= \frac{1}{Re} (\phi'''' - 2\alpha^2 \phi'' + \alpha^4 \phi). \end{aligned} \quad (B4)$$

This is the Orr-Sommerfeld Eigenproblem which determines the linear stability of the base flow.

C. Weakly Nonlinear Expansion

$$u' = \epsilon u_1 + \epsilon^2 u_2 + \epsilon^3 u_3 + \dots \quad (C1)$$

(C1)

with slow time:

$$T = \epsilon^2 t. \quad (C2)$$

The time derivative turns into:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \epsilon^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \quad (C3)$$

C.1 Order ϵ

$$\partial_t u_1 = \mathcal{L}(U)u_1. \quad (C4)$$

Solution:

$$u_1 = A(T) \Phi_1 e^{i\omega t} + c.c. \quad (C5)$$

C.2 Order ϵ^2

$$\partial_t u_2 - \mathcal{L}(U)u_2 = \mathcal{N}(u_1, u_1), \quad (C6)$$

where

$$\mathcal{N}(a, b) = -(a \cdot \nabla)b. \quad (C7)$$

If we substitute C6:

$$\mathcal{N} = A^2 (\Phi_1 \cdot \nabla) \Phi_1 e^{2i\omega t} + |A|^2 \mathcal{N}_0 + c.c. \quad (C8)$$

Thus:

$$u_2 = C(T) \Phi_0 + B(T) \Phi_2 e^{2i\omega t} + c.c. \quad (C9)$$

Φ_0 represents the mean-flow distortion mode generated by the quadratic interaction of the primary mode with its complex conjugate.

With such procedure, the key structural result is:

$$C = \frac{\eta}{\mu} |A|^2 + O(A^4), \quad (C10)$$

showing that mean-flow distortion holds a quadratically primary amplitude.

C.3 Order ϵ^3 - Secular Terms

$$\partial_t u_3 - \mathcal{L}u_3 = -\partial_T u_1 + \mathcal{N}(u_1, u_2) + \mathcal{N}(u_2, u_1). \quad (C11)$$

ω -frequency contribution must vanish: Resonant terms which are proportional to $e^{i\omega t}$ produces a secular growth unless eliminated. To prevent unbounded solutions, the forcing must be orthogonal to the adjoint eigenmode Ψ_1 :

$$\langle \Psi_1, RHS(\omega) \rangle = 0. \quad (C12)$$

This solvability condition yields the amplitude equation.

D. Amplitude Equation Derivation

Compute:

(i) Term from Slow-time Derivation

$$-\partial_T u_1 = -\dot{A}(T) \Phi_1 e^{i\omega t}. \quad (D1)$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle \Psi_1, -\partial_T u_1 \rangle = -\dot{A} \quad (D2)$$

(ii) Nonlinear mean-flow feedback term

0-mode interacting with ω -mode:

$$\mathcal{N}(u_1, u_2)|_\omega = -\beta CA \Phi_1 e^{i\omega t}. \quad (D3)$$

(iii) Cubic Self-Interaction

$$\mathcal{N}(u_1, u_1)|_\omega = -\alpha |A|^2 A \Phi_1 e^{i\omega t}. \quad (D4)$$

Combined Solvability Condition:

$$\dot{A} = \sigma A \pm \alpha |A|^2 A - \beta CA \quad (D5)$$

E. FFT/DFT Formulation (Modal Extraction)

Let the probe signal be sampled at uniform time intervals Δt over N total samples:

$$u_y(t_n), \quad t_n = n\Delta t, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N-1. \quad (E1)$$

The sampling frequency is

$$f_s = \frac{1}{\Delta t}, \quad (E2)$$

and the discrete frequency resolution is

$$\Delta f = \frac{f_s}{N}. \quad (E3)$$

The discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) of the signal is defined as:

$$\hat{u}(k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} u_y(t_n) e^{-\frac{i2\pi kn}{N}}, \quad f_k = \frac{k}{N\Delta t}. \quad (E4)$$

Only the positive-frequency branch carries independent information because the signal is real value.

The modal amplitude is obtained by using the normalization:

$$|\hat{u}(k)|_{phys} = \frac{|\hat{u}(k)|}{N}. \quad (E5)$$

When applied,

$$A = |\hat{u}(\omega = k_1)|, \quad B = |\hat{u}(2\omega = k_1)|, \quad C = |\hat{u}(0)|. \quad (E6)$$

$$k_1 = \text{round}\left(\frac{f_1}{\Delta f}\right) \quad (E7)$$

$$k_2 = \text{round}\left(\frac{2f_1}{\Delta f}\right) \quad (E8)$$

F. Extracted Modal Amplitudes from CFD

Re	A (Primary)	B (2ω Harmonic)	C (Mean Offset)	f_1 (Hz)
60	0.010320	0.000425	0.000463	1.210
80	0.059750	0.001005	0.001038	1.943
100	0.089260	0.001570	~0.00180	2.670
120	0.089230	0.000631	0.002395	3.368